

Scope & Topics

International Journal of Soft Computing, Mathematics and Control (IJSCMC) is a Quarterly peer-reviewed and refereed open access journal that publishes articles which contribute new results in all areas of Soft Computing, Pure, Applied and Numerical Mathematics and Control. The focus of this new journal is on all theoretical and numerical methods on soft computing, mathematics and control theory with applications in science and industry. The goal of this journal is to bring together researchers and practitioners from academia and industry to focus on latest topics of soft computing, pure, applied and numerical mathematics and control engineering, and establishing new collaborations in these areas.

Authors are solicited to contribute to this journal by submitting articles that illustrate new algorithms, theorems, modelling results, research results, projects, surveying works and industrial experiences that describe significant advances in Soft Computing, Mathematics and Control Engineering

Topics of interest include but are not limited to, the following

- Abstract Algebra and Applications
- Adaptive control
- Agriculture, environment, health applications
- Algorithms
- Applications of modelling in science and engineering
- Artificial Neural Networks (ANN)
- Computational Complexity
- Computer modelling
- Control theory
- Differential Geometry
- Digital control
- Discrete Mathematics
- Embedded systems
- Evolutionary algorithms
- Fault detection and isolation
- Feedback control
- Functional Analysis
- Fuzzy logic and applications
- Fuzzy set theory
- Genetic Algorithms
- Genetic algorithms and evolutionary computing
- Graph Theory and Applications
- Hybrid systems
- Industry, military, space applications
- Linear and nonlinear control systems
- Linear and Nonlinear Programming
- Markov Chains and Applications
- Mathematical modelling
- Model predictive control
- Networked control systems
- Neural networks and fuzzy logic
- Neuro-Fuzzy Control
- Numerical Analysis
- Numerical analysis and scientific computing
- Operations Research
- Optimal Control
- Optimization and optimal control
- Optimization Theory
- Ordinary and Partial Differential Equations
- Process control and instrumentation
- Real and Complex Analysis
- Real-time issues
- Robust control
- Scientific computing

- Set Theory
- Sliding mode control
- Soft computing and control
- Statistics
- Stochastic control and filtering
- Stochastic Modelling
- System identification and control
- Systems and automation
- Topology and Analysis

Paper Submission

Authors are invited to submit papers for this journal through E-mail ijscmcjournal@wireilla.com. Submissions must be original and should not have been published previously or be under consideration for publication while being evaluated for this Journal. For paper format download the template in this page.

Important Dates

- **Submission Deadline : May 28, 2022**
- Notification : June 28, 2022
- Final Manuscript Due : July 05, 2022
- Publication Date : Determined by the Editor-in-Chief

Contact Us:

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